

The Nominal HIPPARCOS Scanning Law

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It is desirable to have a simple, explicit analytical expression for the three-axis nominal attitude as function of time. This is needed e.g. for calculating in advance the Program Star File and possibly for modelling and predicting perturbations. The current descriptions of the nominal scanning (SRD 6.1.2.5; E21-HIP-00767, 2.3.1; etc) are still ambiguous in the following respects:

- (i) What exactly is meant by the "satellite/sun line", about which the spin axis is to revolve?
- (ii) How can a constant spin rate be implemented in a simple scanning law? I.e., what is the law for the rotation about the spin axis?

I propose the following clarification of the nominal scanning law:

1. The nominal sun. The centre of the revolving motion should not be the true satellitocentric direction to the sun, but a "nominal sun direction" defined by a simple analytical formula. In particular, the daily parallax ($\pm 58''$), motion about the Earth-Moon barycentre ($\pm 6''$), etc can be ignored in view of the much larger ($\pm 10'$) tolerance for the actual attitude w.r.t. the nominal. The nominal sun direction could for instance be defined as

$$\underline{s}(t) = \underline{i} \cos \lambda_s + \underline{j} \sin \lambda_s \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{K} = [\underline{i} \quad \underline{j} \quad \underline{k}]$ is the ecliptical coordinate triad for the mean ecliptic and equinox of J2000.0, and

$$\lambda_s = L + 2e \sin g + \frac{5}{4} e^2 \sin 2g \quad (2a)$$

$$L = -1.38691 + 0.0172021240 d \quad (2b)$$

$$g = -0.04114 + 0.0172019696 d \quad (2c)$$

$$e = 0.016714 \quad (2d)$$

are respectively the longitude of the nominal sun, the apparent mean longitude of the sun (the geometrical mean longitude minus the aberration constant), the mean anomaly, and the eccentricity. d is the time in days from J1988.0 $\approx$ 1988 Jan 1, 12^h UT.

Remark: Celestial directions should always refer either to $\underline{K}$ or (preferably) to the mean equatorial system at the epoch J2000.0, $\underline{N} = [\underline{l} \quad \underline{m} \quad \underline{n}]$. Here, $\underline{l}$ is the unit vector towards the mean vernal equinox of J2000.0 and $\underline{n}$, $\underline{k}$ the unit vectors towards the north equatorial and ecliptical pole, respectively. The two systems are related by the exact transformation

$$\underline{K} = \underline{N} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \epsilon & -\sin \epsilon \\ 0 & \sin \epsilon & \cos \epsilon \end{bmatrix} = \underline{N} \underline{A}_1(\epsilon) \quad (3)$$

with $\epsilon = 23^\circ 26' 21''.448$. $\underline{A}_1(\epsilon)$ is the (3,3)-matrix representing a rotation through the angle ϵ about the first axis of the preceding coordinate triad.

2. Heliotropic attitude angles. Following a suggestion by F van Leeuwen (1983 Sept 9), we may describe the nominal attitude w.r.t. $\underline{s}$ by means of three angles ξ , ν , and Ω . The first two have their usual meaning, while the third is the angle (in the plane containing the two viewing directions) from the nominal sun to the $\underline{x}$ axis (bisecting the basic angle). It can be noted that the main thermal and radiation pressure perturbations are strictly periodic in Ω . I propose that $\Omega(t)$ is prescribed to increase uniformly with time, at a rate of 168.56 "/s, whereby the inertial rotation about $\underline{z}$ is nominally maintained at 168.75 ± 0.06 "/s. The complete nominal scanning law is then (Lindgren, 1982 June 2):

$$\xi = 43^\circ \quad (4a)$$

$$\nu = \bar{\nu} - 0.16378 \cos \bar{\nu} - 0.01308 \sin 2\bar{\nu} + 0.00123 \cos 3\bar{\nu} + 0.00012 \sin 4\bar{\nu} \quad (4b)$$

$$\bar{\nu} = \bar{\nu}_0 + 6.4 \lambda_s \quad (4c)$$

$$\Omega = \Omega_0 + \dot{\Omega} d, \quad \dot{\Omega} = 168.56 \text{ "/s} \quad (4d)$$

in which only the initial conditions $(\bar{\nu}_0, \Omega_0)$ remain unspecified.

Let $\underline{Z} = [\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$ be the coordinate triad defined by the optical system (X_P, Y_P, Z_P in MATRA's notation): $\underline{x}$ is the bisector of the two viewing directions and $\underline{z}$ their normal on the sunny side. The transformation from $\underline{K}$ to $\underline{Z}$ can now be written

$$\underline{Z} = \underline{K} \underline{A}_3(\lambda_s) \underline{A}_1(\nu - \frac{1}{2}\pi) \underline{A}_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi) \underline{A}_3(\Omega)$$

$$= \underline{K} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \lambda_s & -\sin \lambda_s & 0 \\ \sin \lambda_s & \cos \lambda_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sin \nu & \cos \nu \\ 0 & -\cos \nu & \sin \nu \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \xi & 0 & \cos \xi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\cos \xi & 0 & \sin \xi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \Omega & -\sin \Omega & 0 \\ \sin \Omega & \cos \Omega & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

If $\underline{\omega}$ is the inertial rotation of $\underline{Z}$ and $\omega_x = \underline{x}'\underline{\omega}$, $\omega_y = \underline{y}'\underline{\omega}$, $\omega_z = \underline{z}'\underline{\omega}$ its components w.r.t. $\underline{Z}$, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_z & \omega_y \\ \omega_z & 0 & -\omega_x \\ -\omega_y & \omega_x & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \underline{Z}'\dot{\underline{Z}} \quad (6)$$

from which we find

$$\omega_x = (-\cos \xi \sin \nu \cos \Omega - \cos \nu \sin \Omega) \dot{\lambda}_s - \sin \Omega \dot{\xi} + \sin \xi \cos \Omega \dot{\nu} \quad (7a)$$

$$\omega_y = (\cos \xi \sin \nu \sin \Omega - \cos \nu \cos \Omega) \dot{\lambda}_s - \cos \Omega \dot{\xi} - \sin \xi \sin \Omega \dot{\nu} \quad (7b)$$

$$\omega_z = \sin \xi \sin \nu \dot{\lambda}_s + \cos \xi \dot{\nu} + \dot{\Omega} \quad (7c)$$

Thus, for the proposed scanning law, the inertial rotation about $\underline{z}$ becomes

$$\omega_z = \dot{\Omega} + 6.4 \dot{L} \cos \xi + (1.0482 \cos \xi + \sin \xi) \dot{L} \sin \bar{\nu} + \dots \quad (8)$$

This is offset from $\dot{\Omega}$ by $K \dot{L} \cos \xi$ (the projection of the precession velocity $\dot{s}\bar{\nu}$ on $\underline{z}$); in addition there are periodic variations with amplitudes ≤ 0.06 "/s. For $\omega_z = 168.75$ "/s we should consequently choose

$$\dot{\Omega} = \omega_z - K \dot{L} \cos \xi \approx 168.56 \text{ "/s} \quad (9)$$

FIGURE. Definition of heliotropic attitude angles (ξ , ν , Ω) with respect to the nominal sun direction ($\underline{s}$).